

REVIEW ARTICLE

**UNCOVERING THE MEDICINAL SECRETS OF *TURNERA ULMIFOLIA*:
A PHARMACOLOGICAL OVERVIEW****Deepak Muthu S^{*1}, Nithyapriya R² and Jainambu Beevi S²**¹Department of Pharmacognosy, College of Pharmacy,
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Madras Medical College, Chennai-600003, Tamilnadu, India*Corresponding author E-mail: sachindeepak291@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15564350>**Abstract:**

Turnera ulmifolia Linn, also known as Chanana, belongs to the Passifloraceae family. This plant has a sufficient number of pharmacological effects such as constipation, diarrhea, cold, flu, heart palpitations, menstrual cramps, etc. Various researches have shown that this plant contains a large quantity of chemical constituents such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, cyanogenic glucosides, proteins, amino acids, triterpenoids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds and tannins. Parts have a wide range of positive effects such as anti-bacterial, antioxidant, antifungal and anti-cancer activity. In this text, we have summarized the phytochemicals and pharmacological activity of the plant with the aim of future requirements

Keyword: *Turnera ulmifolia*, Alkaloids, Amino Acids, Phytochemicals, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Cancer, Pharmacological Action.

Introduction:

Prior to the usage of synthetic drugs, humans depended on therapeutic qualities of herbal remedies. Plants are meant to provide humans with nourishment, healing remedies and other benefits. The World Health Organization suggests that around 80% of these individuals mainly depend on traditional medicine for their primary health requirements (Ahvazi M *et al.*, 2012).

Turnera ulmifolia is herbaceous perennial plant that continuously blooms and thrives in ruderal conditions. *Turnera ulmifolia* is capable of self-pollinating and its short lived populations with a moderate level of inbreeding (Laurich JR *et al.*, 2022). Under the microscope, the leaf of *Turnera ulmifolia* displayed numerous stellate non-glandular trichomes, anisocytic stomata and large number of calcium oxalate crystals along the veins (Kumar S *et al.*, 2025).

T. ulmifolia commonly used for Its medicinal properties as an anti-inflammatory, expectorant and in treating various conditions (Hosamani KM, 1993). *T. ulmifolia* is used for indigestion, bronchitis, laxative, carminative, it reduces the fever, used as tonic for indigestion, and it also used for treating cancer and diabetes (Kumar D *et al.*, 2012; Antônio MA *et al.*, 1998).

Taxonomical classification

Domain: Eukaryota

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Spermatophyta

Sub-phylum: Angiospermae

Class: Dicotyledonae

Order: Violales

Family: Turneraceae

Genus: *Turnera*

Species: *Turnera ulmifolia* (Rojas-Sandoval J and Acevedo-Rodríguez P, 2022).

Vernacular names

- English: buttercup flower; false damiana; sage rose
- Spanish: clavel de oro; damiana; escoba amarilla
- Brazil: chanana; relogio
- Germany: Turnera, Ulmenblattrige
- Mexico: Calendula
- USA: Gujg
- India: Cuban buttercup (Rojas-Sandoval J and Acevedo-Rodríguez P, 2022).

Origin

T. ulmifolia is the native species of Mexico, West Indies and Central America (Chandrasekhar N and Vinay S. P, 2017).

Distribution

T. ulmifolia is widely distributed in Brazil, Caribbean region, India, Sri Lanka, Australia, Singapore, Indonesia (Saswoti Patra and Sunita Bhatnagar, 2016; Chandrasekhar N and Vinay S. P, 2017).

Description

- **Leaves:** Leaves out as simple, arranged in pairs opposite each other, before transitioning to alternate placement with short stalks. The leaf blade is oval shaped with a narrowed base and pointed tip. The edge shows variable in size 4 to 12cm long and 1 to 5cm wide.
- **Stem:** The stem is round, firm, ranging from 4 to 10mm in width and extensively divided. Simple appressed hairs, along with short and curved hairs and glandular hairs cover the young stem.
- **Flower:** Located at the bottom of the peduncle the two lanceolate bracts, covered with tiny reddish dots, measuring 12 to 29 mm in length and 2 to 5 mm in width, found specifically at the flower's base. The 3cm long calyx contains 5 sepals fused at the base, terminating in 5 large lanceolate acute tines. The corolla is made up of 5 big petals, much larger than calyx, ranging from 16 to 27mm in length and 7 to 13 mm in width, ovate in shape, very bright yellow, with hair on both sides and having a clawed base.

- **Fruit:** The fruit is nearly round or broadly oval capsule, with 3 compartments, measuring 3 to 8 mm in length and 4 mm in width, opening at the top in three valves with turned tips, rough and heavily coated with tiny bumps at the tip, holding many seeds.
- **Seeds:** Seed shaped like an oval or enlarged at one end, slightly curved, measuring 2 mm in length and 1 mm in width. The seed cot is heavily interconnected and decorated with longitudinal lines of rectangular pits (Curtis W *et al.*, 1801).

Therapeutic potential of *Turnera ulmifolia*

1. Antimicrobial activity

Multiple studies have investigated the antimicrobial activity of ethanolic and methanolic extracts of *Turnera ulmifolia* against various microbial strains and standard Streptomycin with various concentrations. Ethanolic extracts which are used to identify zone of inhibition on multiple microbial strain such as, *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Trichoderma viride*. As a result, *Staphylococcus aureus* shows the maximum zone of inhibition (18mm). in 60 µl concentration against the standard (8mm). followed by 20µl and 40µl concentration.

In methanolic extracts of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Staphylococcus pyogenes*, *Candida albicans*, *Trichoderma viride* strains are compared with standard streptomycin. As a result, shows zone of inhibition of *Klebsiella pneumonia* (22mm). in 60µl followed by 40µl concentration (20mm). and 20µl and 20µl concentration (18mm). against the standard Streptomycin (8mm). (Kalimuthu *et al.*, 2016).

Another study shows ethanolic extracts of *Turnera ulmifolia* leaf against multiple microbial strains with various concentrations. The standard one is Rifampicin (30µg/ml). five different bacterial strains are used as test. In this study *S.typhi* have a higher zone of inhibition (30.76mm). in 40µg/ml. In the case of *E.coli* have 28.81mm in 40µg/ml (Kalimuthu K and Prabakaran R, 2014).

2. Antifungal activity

Ethanol extracts from *Mentha arvensis* and *Turnera ulmifolia* were tested for antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida krusei*. No significant antifungal activity was shown by the extracts, but a synergistic effect was seen when applied with metronidazole against *Candida tropicalis*. *Mentha arvensis* and *Turnera ulmifolia* may offer natural products that have adjustable antifungal properties (Santos *et al.*, 2012).

3. Antiulcerogenic activity

Turnera ulmifolia is commonly used in traditional Brazilian medicine to treat conditions related to GIT problems such as gastric and duodenal ulcers. This research examined the potential of a free-dried infusion from the aerial parts of *T. ulmifolia*, known as the aqueous fraction, to protect the gastric and duodenal mucosa from ulcers in mice and rats. The AqF showed a significant decrease lesions caused by HCl/ethanol administration by 39% and 46% at doses of 500mg/kg and 100mg/kg given orally. The AqF also markedly decreased the occurrence of stomach injuries caused by mix if indomethacin and bethanechol by 58% and 72% at 500mg/kg and 1000mg/kg doses. The AqF showed a 48% reduction in stress-induced gastric ulcer at 250 mg/kg, 57% at 500 mg/kg, and 58% at 1000mg/kg

doses ($p < 0.05$). AN experiment with a pyloric ligature demonstrated that the maximum dosage of AqF had a notable impact on gastric juice parameters, raising the pH 2.5(control). to 5.3 and reducing the acid output from 11.3(control). to 3.7 mEq/ml/4h. The AqF did not cause any notable impact on cysteamine-induced duodenal ulcers. Initial testing showed that the main component of the water extract of *Turnera ulmifolia* was flavonoids (Gracioso J de S *et al.*, 2002).

4. Antibacterial activity

This research involves determining the antibacterial activity exhibits by leaf extracts of *Turnera ulmifolia* against the pathogenic bacteria such as, *Salmonella typhi*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*. Ciprofloxacin was standard for comparison. DMSO is used as solvent. The *invitro* test has performed by disc diffusion method (Poonam Sethi *et al.*, 2011). Bacteria utilized in current research was prone to reacting to the ethanolic extracts from the plant demonstrated possible effects. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* shows the maximum zone of inhibition 32mm (30µg/ml). *Salmonella typhi* and *E.coli* shows the minimum inhibitory zone 80µg/ml & 60µg/ml. This plant exhibits antibacterial properties would aid in the advancements of a medicine system without any adverse effects (Lin J *et al.*, 1999).

Another study, antibacterial activities of silver nanoparticles exhibit by *Argemone mexicana* and *Turnera ulmifolia* flowers assessed by the disc diffusion method (Murali Krishna *et al.*, 2015). Various microbes such as *K.aerogenes*, *P.aeruginosa*, *E.coli*, *S.aureus* were used to determine the antibacterial activity against silver nanoparticles. As a result, *Turnera ulmifolia* has maximum zone of inhibition (27mm). than *Argemone mexicana* has minimum zone of inhibition (20-24mm). Based on results, silver nanoparticles derived from *Turnera ulmifolia* have been shown to exhibit antibacterial activity (Chandrasekhar N and Vinay SP, 2017).

5. Anti-Inflammatory activity

The research tested the preventative anti-inflammatory effects on the intestines using a lyophilized infusion from the aerial parts of *Turnera ulmifolia* in a rat colitis model induced by trinitrobenzene sulphonic acid. The results showed that giving colitic rats the extract before, at doses of 250 & 500 mg/kg significantly reduced the colonic damage caused by TNBS. This positive impact was linked to an enhancement in the colonic oxidative state, as the enhancement in the colonic oxidative state, as the infusion stopped the reduction of glutathione caused by colonic inflammatory (Galvez J *et al.*, 2006).

Another research involves hydroalcoholic extraction & partitioned fractions of aerial parts of *Turnera ulmifolia* conducted on rats or mice and it exhibits the anti-inflammatory effects and anti-edematogenic effects. 70% crude hydroalcoholic extraction of the plant reducing the inflammation. *Turnera ulmifolia* extracts exhibited anti-edematogenic effect on paw edema induced by carrageenan but it was less effective and enhanced by diclofenac, which was used as control drug. The peak impact of the extract was experienced after 3 hours following administration of the phlogistic agent at a dose of 2000mg/kg, the inhibition was slightly greater than the 1000mg/kg dosage (Antônio MA and Souza Brito ARM, 1998).

6. Anthelmintic activity

An anthelmintic activity of *Turnera ulmifolia* was established by Egg hatching assay. In this method, eggs were dried 3 times to remove the salt & placed in the distilled water. 100 eggs were suspended on plate with 1ml of methanol at 2% and ethanolic leaf extract of *Turnera ulmifolia* and *P.platycephala* added to the treatment. The plate was placed in the 27°C temperature. The most potent egg hatching inhibition was observed in the ethanolic extracts of *Turnera ulmifolia* leaves, with an IC₅₀ value of 430µg/ml, while the ethanolic extracts of *P.platycephala* seeds showed lower inhibition IC₅₀ value of 1170-1550µg/ml (Oliveira A F et al., 2017).

7. Antioxidant activity

The antioxidant activity of *Turnera ulmifolia* 50% hydroethanolic extract was tested using the β-carotene/linoleic acid oxidation system invitro to assess its ability to prevent oxidation and lipid peroxidation in rat brain homogenates, measured through Thio barbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS). and chemiluminescence (CL). Findings showed that this extract displayed higher antioxidant activity (77.4% ± 10%). than α-tocopherol (58.4% ± 3.7%). due to its peroxidation inhibition (Nascimento MA et al., 2006).

Hydroethanolic extracts of leaves of *Turnera ulmifolia* show antioxidant properties. Free Radical Scavenging Assay which helps to determine the invitro antioxidant activity by using hydroethanolic extract of *Turnera ulmifolia*. Additionally, levels of glutathione and activities of antioxidant enzymes (glutathione, peroxidase, superoxide dismutase, catalase). were notably increased in rats treated with CCl₄ after receiving hydroethanolic extraction of *Turnera ulmifolia* orally (500 mg/kg). for 7&21 days (Brito N J N et al., 2012).

8. Antidiabetic activity

Methanolic extracts of *Turnera ulmifolia* leaves showed anti-hyperglycemic activity in alloxan induced rats. At a dose of 100mg/kg of body weight, the extract caused a mild effect. 200mg/kg of body weight resulted in moderately effective in diabetic rats and increased dosage maximum effect was observed at a dosage of 400mg/kg of body weight. Rats are treated with alloxan who are receiving the extraction of leaves from *Turnera ulmifolia* exhibited quick stabilization of blood glucose levels in comparison to the glibenclamide (Prabu D et al., 2009).

9. Anticancer activity

To assess the cytotoxic effects, the extracts were examined at different concentrations on both MCF7 human breast cancer cells and normal cells. Cell viability was examined with the end point MTT assay after 48 hours. After 48 hours of treatment (18.75-300µg/ml)., a few cells started to separate from the plate and take on a round shape. Different levels of cytotoxicity were exhibited by all the samples, including cell rounding, shrinkage, aggregation and cell death, which is based on the concentration of the extracts. The samples demonstrated a higher cytotoxic effect at a concentration of 300µg/ml, as shown by the greater quantity of death cells. The extracts from the callus showed higher cytotoxicity towards human breast cancer cells with an IC₅₀ value greater than 300µg/ml (Kalimuthu K et al., 2016).

Conclusion:

In conclusion, *Turnera ulmifolia* has demonstrated a wide range of pharmacological properties, making it a valuable plant in traditional and modern medicine. From antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects to antioxidant and anticancer activities, its bioactive compounds offer promising therapeutic potential. As research continues to uncover its medicinal benefits, this review highlights the necessity of further investigations into its clinical applications and mechanisms of action. Harnessing the properties of *Turnera ulmifolia* could pave the way for novel natural treatments that enhance healthcare solutions globally.

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